

ANNUAL REPORT

2024-25

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title	Page
Vision, Mission and Quality Policy	01
Executive Summary	02
University Rankings	03
Academics	05
Students	09
33 rd Convocation	11
Scholarships & Financial Assistance	12
Industrial Experiences	13
Community Service Programme	15
International Students	17
Co- and Extra-curricular Activities	18
Sports	26
Faculty statistics	28
Faculty Mobility	32
Public and Social Service	33
Representation on Universities Statutory & Technical Forums	34
Faculty Awards	35

Title	Page
Research	37
Research Centres	38
Research Grants	39
Research Publications	40
Patents	41
Research Journals	43
International Conferences	44
University Impact	46
Strategic Plan 2024-29	51
Carbon Footprint Profile	54
University Support Functions	56
ORIC	56
Business Incubation Centre	60
Engr. Abul Kalam Library	61
Quality Assurance	64
NED Academy	66
Information Technology	67
Medical Department	69
UAFA	70
National Incubation Centre	72
Outreach and Networking	73
Collaborations and Linkages	73
Prominent Visitors	76
Alumni Engagement & Support	79
Special Mentions	80
University Finances and KPIs	84

VISION

Be a leader in enabling Pakistan's social and economic transformation.

MISSION

Acquire education and research excellence in engineering and allied disciplines to produce leadership and enabling application of knowledge and skills for the benefit of the society with integrity and wisdom.

QUALITY POLICY

NED University of Engineering and Technology believes in establishing environment conducive to continual improvement in its efforts for providing the highest-level of quality education.

The university is making all out efforts to raise its standards through teaching excellence and quality research. These efforts are carried out with involvement of the entire University work force to obtain utmost possible satisfaction of its customers.

Our endeavours are to make our students useful to society in particular and to humanity in general. In dealing with industries and utilities, attempts are made to maintain standards of integrity as well as quality.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Welcome to the 2024–25 Annual Report of NED University of Engineering and Technology. This report presents a comprehensive account of the University's achievements, growth, and impact over the past year. NED University continues to uphold its legacy of excellence in higher education. In the Times Higher Education World Impact Rankings, the University was ranked among the top 800 institutions globally, with standout performance in specific categories: Top 200 in Affordable and Clean Energy and Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure | Top 300 in Quality Education.

This year also marked the launch of first year of our first-ever Five-Year Strategic Plan, setting ambitious targets across 12 strategic pillars aligned with five strategic objectives, reaffirming our commitment to sustainable and high-quality education.

Our academic portfolio expanded to offer 117 degree programs, attracting 11,589 students. At the 33rd Convocation, we proudly conferred degrees on 1,930 graduates, including 20 PhDs. In a significant achievement, 100% of our undergraduate students received scholarships and fellowships amounting to Rs. 378 million, ensuring equitable access to education. We also welcomed 58 international students and enhanced global student mobility.

The University's academic and research excellence is powered by 518 faculty members, of whom 244 hold PhD degrees. This year, we established three new centres, bringing the total to 31 centres, and continued work on 233 funded projects with a cumulative value of approximately Rs. 2 billion. We also hosted thirteen international conferences, providing vibrant forums for global knowledge exchange.

Strong national and international linkages further bolstered our academic profile. Notably, the Centre for Environment and Social Sustainability (CESS) was launched this year with support from the World Bank, underscoring our leadership in sustainability. Progress was also made on the NED Technology Park, and the PHWI continued to advance capacity-building programs.

Alumni contributions remain a cornerstone of NED's growth. Our alumni supported key initiatives such as campus solarization, city campus renovation by Engr. Ashraf Habibullah, smart classrooms, scholarships, lab enhancements, and STEM outreach. A milestone event this year was the NEDIAN Alumni Convention 2025, held in February, which brought together our global alumni community.

The achievements highlighted in this report are a testament to the dedication of our faculty, staff, students, alumni, and partners. Their collective efforts continue to shape NED University as a leader in engineering and technology education in Pakistan and beyond.

We invite you to explore this year's milestones and success stories in the pages ahead.

Happy reading!

GEARING GROWTH IN UNIVERSITY RANKINGS

The World University Rankings **1500+**

Asia University Rankings **601+**

Engineering and Technology Rankings **1001+**

Times World Impact Ranking 2025

401-600

TOP 200

09 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE

An icon consisting of three white cubes stacked together on an orange background.

TOP 200

07 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY

An icon of a white power button symbol on a brown background.

TOP 200

04 QUALITY EDUCATION

An icon of a white open book and a pen on a dark red background.

TOP 400

01 NO POVERTY

An icon of white silhouettes of a family (two adults and two children) on a red background.

TOP 400

06 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION

An icon of a white water tap with a drop of water on a blue background.

TOP 500

QS Asian Rankings 2024

926

World University Ranking

787

Research
Rankings

867

International
Diversity

588

Financial
Sustainability

894

Academic
Ranking

**RESEARCH
INNOVATION AND
COMMERCIALIZATION 2024-25**

**Top 5
out of 200+**

Overall ranking in Research,
Innovation & Commercialization
"W" Category

2nd

Ranking in HR
and Operations

3rd

Ranking in
Research
Excellence

4th

Ranking in
Innovation and
Commercialization

ACADEMIC PROGRAMMES

NED University has 30 teaching departments from five faculties and one constituent college - TIEST, offering 35 undergraduate, 61 masters and 21 Ph.D. programmes – thus a total of 117 programmes are currently being offered.

NED University has decided to transform all undergraduate engineering programmes on outcome-based education (OBE). All undergraduate engineering programmes have already obtained OBE-based accreditation from Pakistan Engineering Council (PEC).

05

Faculties

30

**Teaching
Departments**

01

**Constituent
College**

35

**Bachelors
Programmes**

61

**Masters
Programmes**

21

**Ph.D.
Programmes**

FACULTY OF CIVIL AND PETROLEUM ENGINEERING

DEPARTMENT	UNDERGRADUATE	MASTERS	PH.D.
Civil Engineering	B.E. Civil Engineering B.E. Civil Engineering (specialization in Construction)	M. Engg. Structural Engineering M. Engg. Geo-Tech Engineering M. Engg. Transportation Engg. M. Engg. Coastal & Water Resources Engineering MEM Construction Management MEM Water Resources Mgt.	Yes
Urban and Infrastructure Engineering	B.E. Civil Engineering (specialization in Urban)	MEM Transportation Infrastructure Management	Yes
Petroleum Engineering	B.E. Petroleum Engineering	M. Engg. Petroleum Engineering	-
Earthquake Engineering	-	M. Engg. Structural Earthquake Engineering	Yes
Environmental Engineering	-	M. Engg. Environmental Engineering MEM Environmental Management	Yes

INSTITUTE	MASTERS
Panjwani-Hisar Water Institute (PHWI)	MEM Urban Water Management MEM Climate Change Management

FACULTY OF MECHANICAL AND MANUFACTURING ENGINEERING

DEPARTMENT	UNDERGRADUATE	MASTERS	PH.D.
Mechanical Engineering	B.E. Mechanical Engineering	M. Engg. Design M. Engg. Energy Systems M. Engg. Mechatronics M. Engg. Renewable Energy MEM Energy and Plant Management	Yes
Textile Engineering	B.E. Textile Engineering B.S. Textile Sciences	M. Engg. Textile Engineering MEM Textile Management MS Textile Management	Yes
Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering	B.E. Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering	M. Engg. Manufacturing Engineering MEM Industrial Management MEM Quality Management MEM Supply Chain Management	Yes
Automotive & Marine Engg.	B.E. Automotive Engineering	M. Engg. Automotive Design M. Engg. Automotive Manufacturing	-

FACULTY OF CHEMICAL AND PROCESS ENGINEERING

DEPARTMENT	UNDERGRADUATE	MASTERS	PH.D.
Chemical Engineering	B.E. Chemical Engineering	M. Engg. Chemical Engineering MEM Chemical and Process Mngmt.	Yes
Materials Engineering	B.E. Materials Engineering	M. Engg. Materials Engineering	Yes
Metallurgical Engineering	B.E. Metallurgical Engineering	M.Engg. Metallurgical Engineering	Yes
Polymer and Petrochemical Engineering	B.E. Polymer and Petrochemical Engineering	M. Engg. Polymer Engineering	Yes
Food Engineering	B.E. Food Engineering	-	-

FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE AND SCIENCES

DEPARTMENT	UNDERGRADUATE	MASTERS	PH.D.
Architecture and Planning	B. Architecture B.S. Development Studies	Master of Urban and Regional Planning M. Arch. Architecture	Yes
Economics and Management Sciences	B.S. Economics and Finance B.S. Management Sciences	MS Economics and Finance	-
Physics	B.S. Applied Physics	MS Physics MS Optics MS Medical Physics	Yes
Chemistry	B.S. Industrial Chemistry	MS Industrial Chemistry	Yes
Mathematics	-	MS in Applied Mathematics	Yes
English Linguistics & Allied Studies	B.S. English Linguistics	MS Applied Linguistics	Yes
Essential Studies	The Department offers essential studies courses in the University		

FACULTY OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING

DEPARTMENT	UNDERGRADUATE	MASTERS	PH.D.
Electrical Engineering	B.E. Electrical Engineering	M. Engg. Electrical Power Systems M. Engg. Control Systems M. Engg. Electrical Machines & Drives M. Engg. Smart Grid MEM Energy Management	Yes
Computer and Information Systems Engineering	B.E. Computer Systems Engineering	M. Engg. Computer Architecture & Systems Design M. Engg. Computer Network & System Security MS Data Engineering and Information Management MS Artificial Intelligence	Yes
Electronic Engineering	B.E. Electronic Engineering	M. Engg. Integrated Circuit Design M. Engg. Industrial Electronics	Yes
Telecommunications Engineering	B.E. Telecommunications Engineering	M. Engg. Telecommunications Engineering a) RF Engineering b) Telecommunications Networks MS Telecommunications Systems	Yes
Biomedical Engineering	B.E. Biomedical Engineering	M. Engg. Biomedical Engineering	Yes
Software Engineering	B.E. Software Engineering	M. Engg. Software Engineering	Yes
Computer Science & Information Technology	B.S. CSIT B.S. CSIT (AI) B.S. CSIT (Cyber Security) B.S. CSIT (Data Analytics) B.S. CSIT (Gaming & Animation)	MS Computer Science and Information Technology MS Information Security MS Data Sciences Geospatial Data Science	Yes

THAR INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING, SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, MITHI, THARPARKAR

DEPARTMENT	UNDERGRADUATE
Department of Computer Science and IT	B.S. Computer Science and Information Technology
Department of Civil Engineering	B.E. Civil Engineering

STUDENTS

13,331
Applicants

3,619
Admissions

11,589
Enrolment

3,015
Graduation

APPLICATIONS	PROGRAMMES	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
	Undergraduate Programmes	7,074	4,368 (38%)	11,442
	Masters Programmes	1,308	495 (27%)	1,803
	Ph.D. Programmes	47	39 (45%)	86
	Total Applicants	8,429	4,902 (37%)	13,331
ADMISSIONS	PROGRAMMES	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
	Undergraduate Programmes	1,329	1,199 (47%)	2,528
	Masters Programmes	754	308 (29%)	1,062
	Ph.D. Programmes	14	15 (52%)	29
	Total Admissions	2,097	1,522 (42%)	3,619
ENROLMENT	PROGRAMMES	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
	Undergraduate Programmes	4,806	4,308 (47%)	9,114
	Enrolment in TIEST	91	43 (32%)	134
	Masters Programmes	1,524	628 (29%)	2,152
	Ph.D. Programmes	106	83 (44%)	189
	Total Enrolment	6,527	5,062 (44%)	11,589
GRADUATION	PROGRAMMES	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
	Undergraduate Programmes	1,172	906 (44%)	2,078
	Masters Programmes	640	276 (30%)	916
	Ph.D. Programmes	14	07 (33%)	21
	Total Graduation	1,826	1,189 (40%)	3,015

33rd CONVOCATION 2024

33rd Convocation of NED University of Engineering and Technology was held on Saturday, the 29th of October 2024. The Chief Guests on the occasion were Mr. Hussain Dawood Chairman, chairman of Engro Holdings and The Dawood Foundation and the honourable Chief Minister of Sindh, Syed Murad Ali Shah, while Engr. Amir ul Islam was the Guest of Honour. The convocation was presided over by the Governor Sindh/Chancellor, Mr. Muhammad Kamran Khan Tessori.

A total of **1930** degrees were awarded during the convocation including **1690** undergraduate, 220 masters and 20 PhD degrees.

Additionally, **90** position holders were awarded gold medals and merit certificates, out of which 65 (72%) were female graduates.

SCHOLARSHIPS AND FINANCIAL ASSISTANCE

This year a total of **12,074** scholarships were awarded worth over Rs. **378** million. It is to be noted that we are reporting two semesters' disbursements for our programmes i.e., Fall 2024 and Spring 2025 along with admissions. Please see table below for details.

SCHOLARSHIP CATEGORY	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL	AMOUNT (PKR)
Private Funded	570	598	1168	101,875,994
Maa Jee Scholarship	125	175	300	26,851,473
Ehsaas Programme	52	54	106	14,840,000
HEC Scholarship	56	100	156	2,500,000
Zakat & Ushr	54	64	118	12,600,000
Sindh HEC	12	13	25	5,750,000
Financial Assistance (Admission Support)	50	57	107	4,423,447
Financial Assistance (Semester Support)	09	10	19	784,171
Duty Society	368	205	573	12,859,243
NED University Undergraduate Fellowship Programme	5,070	4,432	9,502	186,838,848
PhD Fellowships		154		9,240,000
Total				378,563,176

INDUSTRIAL EXPERIENCE

2,716

INTERNSHIPS

1,073

Semester Break,
Vacations

1,643

Ramadan Break

84%

Effective Employment
Rate

133

STUDY TOURS,
INDUSTRIAL VISITS

42

ON-CAMPUS
RECRUITMENT DRIVES

153

FINAL YEAR
DESIGN PROJECTS
FROM INDUSTRIES

550

OTHER EMPLOYMENT
RELATED ENGAGEMENTS,
ACTIVITIES

COOPERATIVE EDUCATION PROGRAMME

The Cooperative Education Programme was introduced at NED University in 2017. It combines classroom learning with practical industry experience throughout a student's four-year degree. Traditional education often lacks a strong link between academic content and real-world industry practices. As a result, many employers need to provide additional training to graduates before they can start working. The Co-op Programme helps bridge this gap by giving students hands-on industry exposure during their studies. Selected students, based on merit, take part in industrial placements during their semester breaks—from their first year until graduation—making the transition from education to employment much smoother.

PARTNER ORGANIZATIONS IN NED UNIVERSITY

Co-op programme

systems

MOUs

SIEMENS

Directorate of Industrial Liaison (DIL) During Year 2024-25

Some of the organizations with whom Directorate of Industrial Liaison remained engaged during the past year for job placements and recruitments

COMMUNITY SERVICE PROGRAMME

INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS

58 International students from 06 different nationalities are currently enrolled in various undergraduate and postgraduate programmes of the University. These nationalities include Somalia, Yemen, Turkey, Afghanistan, Sri Lanka and Kenya.

CO- AND EXTRA-CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

List of events organized by Department of Student Affairs and their respective societies

Department of Student Affairs Events

- “Youm e Istehsal e Kashmir” Awareness Session held on 5th August 2024.
- 77th Pakistan Independence Day Celebrations on 14th August 2024 including:
 - Flag Hoisting Ceremony
 - Independence Day Rally
 - Declamation
 - National Song & Theater Play
 - Sports Competition (Girls & Boys)
- “NED Orientation Programme & Carnival 2024” held on 19th August 2024.
- Anti-Harassment Session with FOSPAH held on 10th September 2024.
- Full Bright & Global UGRAD sessions: 13th Sept, 4th Oct, 12th Nov 2024.
- Higher Studies Sessions (France, Nottingham) in Sept & Oct 2024.
- “RedBull Basement NED Start up Showdown” held on 2nd October 2024.
- “Pakistan Army’s Selection Criteria & Process” held on 3rd October 2024.
- Educational Visits of Baluchistan University, Habib Girls School, Army College, and others from Oct 2024 to Apr 2025.
- “Revitalization The Message of Pakistaniyat” held on 12th November 2024.
- “How to Build a Startup” held on 11th February 2025.
- “US Universities Fair 2025” held on 18th February 2025.
- “Iftar Party at Governor Sindh” held on 8th March 2025.
- Seminars and Sessions on Inclusive Youth, Extremism, Disability Rights (April 2025).
- “Importance of Vaccines on World Immunization Week 2025” on 28th April 2025.
- “Regional Rounds of Debating Championship” held on 15th April 2025.
- Cricket Tournament for Youth Awareness held on 26th April 2025.

Literary & Publications Society (LPS)

- “Baad e Naubahar” – Essay Writing, Mazmoon Nigari, Bait Baazi, Poetry & Arts Competitions held on 1st & 3rd July 2024.
- Essay & Art Competition titled “Journey towards a Peaceful and Stable Country” held on 4th September 2024.
- “Zaawiya Season 5 Episode 1” held on 26th September 2024.
- “Hurf o Hunter” held on 19th November 2024.

Photography Society

- “Photohunt x NPS” held on 4th November 2024.

NSA – Notifying Stories Around Society

- “NED Eats Food Stalls & Students Activities” held on 4th July 2024.
- “NED in Focus: A Walk through Lens” held on 24th September 2024.
- “Olympiad 3.0” Sports Event held from 13th to 15th November 2024.

NED Debating Society

- Speaker Session & National Song Competition on “Youm e Defa” held on 5th September 2024

Green Society

- “Stream of Progress Motivation Session” held on 15th October 2024.
- “NED Plantation Drive 2025” held on 14th January 2025.

Girls Affairs Society

- Youth Awareness Programme on “Breast Cancer” held on 23rd October 2024.
- “Lead Her Ship” programme held on 21st November 2024.

The NEDians Forum Society

- “The Enigma Experience” held on 24th October 2024.
- “NED Athletic Demonstration Session” held on 27th January 2025.
- “NED Athletic” Sports Event held on 28th & 29th January 2025.
- Seminar on “Inclusive Pakistan: Disability Rights Accessibility” held on 21st November 2024.

MOSAIC (Artistic & Intellectual Creativity Society)

- “ViRTous Quest 2.0” (Theater & National Song Competition) held on 4th & 5th November 2024.

Youth Empowerment Club

- “Teacher Tribute Day” held on 8th November 2024.
- “Disasters Management” programme held on 18th November 2024.

Blood Donation Drives Organized by Student Affairs Department

- “The Enigma Experience” held on 24th October 2024.
- “NED Athletic Demonstration Session” held on 27th January 2025.
- “NED Athletic” Sports Event held on 28th & 29th January 2025.
- Seminar on “Inclusive Pakistan: Disability Rights Accessibility” held on 21st November 2024.

TECHNICAL SOCIETIES

American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) NED Student Branch

- 2nd October 2024: Back to Future by Timothy Wentz, Past-President ASHRAE International.
- 3rd October 2024: Inauguration of Anwar Saadat RAC Lab by Dennis Knight, President ASHRAE International.
- 17th February 2025: Explore the power of a scientific calculator – NEDUET Student Branch.
- 7th May 2025: Cooling Load Calculation via Computational Tools – Dr. Haider Ali, Associate Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering.

American Concrete Institute (ACI) NED Student Chapter

- 1st November 2024: Beadbox – Lightweight concrete cube casting event for civil students.
- 25th April 2025: Flexstasy – Bendable concrete beam casting event highlighting ductility.
- 19th April 2025: Site Visit to Bahria Town – Explored mosque, stadium, and STP for architectural and environmental learning.
- 10th April 2025: RE³ Workshop – Guided students on research methodology, writing, and analysis.
- 18th March 2025: Marketing Workshop – Online session on professional marketing skills.
- 9th February 2025: CIVIL SOFTVERSE Launch – Free learning platform for Revit and ETABS; two batches completed.
- 14th March 2025: Ramadan Charity Drive – for TCF to support underprivileged children.
- 19th February 2025: Humans of Civil – Online series featuring civil department personalities.
- 18th–23rd March 2025: Concrete Trivia – Quiz competition testing student knowledge on concrete.
- 5–6th February 2025: Green Construction Conference – ACI NEDUET members volunteered for global sustainability event.
- 15–16th November 2024: 14th ICEC Volunteering – Assisted in organizing international civil engineering conference.
- 15th November 2024: NSA Sports Olympiad Victory – ACI NEDUET won the all-university sports competition.

Institute of Mechanical Engineering IMechE NED Student Chapter

- 6th June 2024: Photography Challenge'24 – Students showcased photography skills.
- 13th June 2024: Abul Kalam Design Challenge AKDC'24 – National event with 14 teams showcasing engineering skills.
- 11th August 2024: Propellair'24 – National RC airplane design and flying competition with 19 teams.
- 25th September 2024: Induction Ceremony – Welcomed new members for the 2023–2024 tenure.
- 25th October 2024: Speak Out for Engineering Nationals'24 – Umme Aiman from IMechE NED emerged as the winner.
- 11th November 2024: Mechathon 9.0 – Flagship event with 128 teams competing across four modules.
- 3rd February 2025: Speak Out for Engineering SOFE'25 – Students articulated ideas on pressing engineering topics.
- 28th April 2025: Photography Challenge'25 – Students displayed creative skills through captivating images.

American Association of Textile Chemists and Colourists AATCC NED Chapter

- 6th July 2024: Annual Retreat 2024 – Well-being retreat at a scenic farmhouse.
- 24–25th August 2024: 9th Color & Chem Expo Participation – Managed AATCC Pakistan Section booth in Lahore.
- 22nd October 2024: Induction Event – Welcomed new members and introduced plans for activities.
- 12th November 2024: Midas Safety Event 2024 – Career event on industry trends and sustainability.
- 13–15th November 2024: Olympiad 4.0 Participation – Won Girls' Sprint and placed in Boys' Table Tennis.
- 12th November 2024: Hassan Ali Khatri's Achievement – Won 3rd place in AATCC Graduate Paper Competition (USA).
- 10th February 2025: Sustainability in Textile Seminar – Sessions on circular fashion and eco-innovation.
- 26th January 2025: Visit to GTex Exhibition – Explored modern textile machinery at Expo Centre, Karachi.
- 21st February 2025: Visit to Indus Motor Company – Observed Toyota production/assembly plant.

- 28th April 2025: Textile Printing Competition – Students displayed diverse printing techniques.
- 30th April 2025: AATCC Career Seminar – Over 200 students explored career options and industry expectations.
- 5th May 2025: NEDUET Alumni Insight – Alumnus Mr. Arif Zaffar Mansuri shared career guidance tips.
- 7th May 2025: Environmental Sustainability Competition – Students showcased eco-friendly projects.

AIChE NED Chapter

- 30th August 2024: Freshers Fest – Ice-breaking event with Scavenger Hunt and Trivia Competition.
- 27th September 2024: Induction Ceremony – Held at Mechanical AV Hall for new members.
- 26th October 2024: Bazm-e-Chemies – Welcome party for members.
- 5th November 2024: Seminar on "Shaping the Future of Chemical Engineers" – Collaborated with ACS NEDUET.
- 20th November 2024: Team Shoots – Professional photoshoot for the student body.
- 18–19th December 2024: Volunteered at ICAMPE 2024 – 4th International Conference on Advanced Materials.
- 17th and 24th January 2025: Industrial Visits to Lucky Core Industries.
- March 2025: Ramadan Donation Drive – Raised over PKR 200,000 for TCF with ACI NEDUET and SPE NEDUET.
- 18th March 2025: Industrial Marketing Workshop – Collaborated with ACI NEDUET and ITE NEDUET.
- Ramadan 2025: Launched "Catalyst Connect" – Alumni network for Chemical Engineering Department.
- 16–18th April 2025: ChemE Nexus – 3-module technical event with safety training and refinery simulation.
- 7th May 2025: Research Workshop – Part of Chemical Symposium 2.0 with Dr. Bilal Kazmi (University of Karachi).

NED Chapter of the American Society of Mechanical Engineering (ASME)

- 26th September 2024: Induction Ceremony – Included session by Ms. Arooba Afridi. 3rd October 2024: Orientation Ceremony.
- 14th October 2024: Informative session on medical hazards for women with Dr. Hina Andani and Dr. Rabia Naz.

- 16th October 2024: Visit to Alsons Industries and GTR (Ghandhara Tyre).
- 31st October 2024: Ignite 9.0 Orientation and Amal Academy Information Session.
- 1st November 2024: Session by Ms. Sheema Ghani on 'Role of Women in Transforming Public Services'.
- 4–6th November 2024: Ignite 9.0 – Flagship event at NED Main Campus.
- 21st January 2025: Visit to Atlas Honda.
- 28th January 2025: Visit to Dawlance Pvt Ltd.
- 12th March 2025: Online talk with Ms. Aiman Shafique on EV industry.
- 2024–2025: Won 'Student Section Achievement Award' and 'Distinguished Student Section Award' (Asia Pacific).

IEEE Power and Energy Society Student Branch NED

- 10th September 2024: Visit to KE Bin Qasim Power Station II (BQPS-II).
- 11–13th February 2025: Electrovision-25 – Mega event with competitions and networking opportunities.
- 23rd January 2025: Industrial visit to KE CCPP Bin Qasim Power Station (BQPS-II and BQPS-III).
- 21st October 2024: Industrial visit to K-Electric (Gulshan-e-Iqbal Grid station).
- 16th October 2024: Seminar on "Introduction to Substations & Networking–Career Guidance" by Mr. Kashif Shamshad (MAK POWER).

SPORTS

CRICKET EVENTS

- 15–23 Jan 2024: Participated in Master Oil University Cricket Championship League, Karachi.
- 01–06 May 2024: Organized Night Cricket Tournament for NED Hostellers.
- 11-May 2024: Friendly Night Cricket match with Sri Lankan students.
- 06-Jun 2024: Friendly cricket match against Bahria University.
- 07-Aug 2024: Night cricket match: NED Sri Lankan vs Dow Sri Lankan students.
- 15–19 Oct 2024: Participated in PCB HEC Intervarsity Cricket (Boys) Zone-M Tournament at IBA Karachi.
- 01–02 Jan 2025: Practice matches for HEC Cricket team selection at NED.
- 06 Jan 2025: HEC selection match at Rashid Latif Cricket Ground.
- 08–11 Jan 2025: HEC Cricket vs Eshaal Asst. at National Bank Stadium.
- 14–17 Jan 2025: HEC Cricket vs KRL at NBP Sports Complex.
- 20–23 Jan 2025: HEC Cricket vs Ghani Glass at UBL Sports Complex.
- 26–27 Jan 2025: More HEC practice matches at NED.
- 01–04 Feb 2025: HEC Cricket vs SBP at SBP Sports Complex.
- 07–10 Feb 2025: HEC Cricket vs SNGPL at UBL Sports Complex.
- 13–16 Feb 2025: HEC Cricket vs PTV at KCCA Stadium.
- 19–22 Feb 2025: HEC Cricket vs WAPDA at KCCA Stadium.
- 25–28 Feb 2025: HEC Cricket vs OGDCL at SBP Sports Complex.
- 24-Apr 2025: Friendly cricket match among NED students.

FOOTBALL EVENTS

- 01 Mar 2024: Friendly football match vs Invaders Football Club.
- 20 Apr 2024: Football match vs Sir Syed University.
- 04 May 2024: Match against 16 Stars Football Club.
- 31 May 2024: Football match vs Indus University.
- 09 Nov 2024: Match vs IoBM Football team.
- 17 Nov 2024: Second football match vs IoBM.

VOLLEYBALL EVENTS

- 12-13 Nov 2024: Hosted and participated in Intervarsity Volleyball (Men) Zone-M Championship.
- 22 Nov 2024: Friendly volleyball match vs IoBM Volleyball team.

OTHER SPORTS AND EVENTS

- 25–29 Jan 2024: Referee Refresher Course & National Karate Championship.
- 24 Feb 2024: Ms. Eisha Iffan represented NED at Aitchison Fastest Men & Women Championships.
- 01 Jun–30 Jul 2024: Archery camp for NED students.
- 07 Aug 2024: Independence Day Sports Celebration (Cricket, Athletics, Badminton, Futsal, Tug of War).
- 24 Apr 2025: Basketball match between NED and Bahria University.

FACULTY STATISTICS

FACULTY	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
Professors	41	04 (9%)	45
Associate Professors	34	16 (32%)	50
Assistant Professors	137	77 (36%)	214
Lecturers	106	104 (50%)	210
TOTAL	318	201 (39%)	519

FACULTY	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
Research Staff	84	59 (41%)	143
PhD Faculty	178	66 (27%)	244
Number of PhD enrolled faculty	31	11 (26%)	42
Number of visiting faculty members at UG and PG	-	-	518

PHD FACULTY

244 – COUNTRY WISE

Canada	06
China	10
Hong Kong	01
Ireland	01
Italy	02
Japan	01
South Korea	08
Portugal	01
Saudi Arabia	03
Turkey	01
Australia	02
Germany	06
Malaysia	25
Netherlands	02
New Zealand	10
Norway	01
Oman	01
Pakistan	132
Sweden	01
UK	44
USA	13

 PHD Faculty

PHD ENROLLED FACULTY

COUNTRY WISE - 42

Australia 02

Germany 01

Malaysia 01

Netherlands 02

New Zealand 03

Norway 01

Oman 01

Pakistan 23

Sweden 01

UK 05

USA 02

PHD Enrolled Faculty

NUMBER OF PHD QUALIFIED FACULTY OVER YEARS

RATIO OF PHD FACULTY OVER ALL FACULTY OVER THE YEARS

FACULTY SERVICE

19 Journals as Editor/Associate Editor

21 Faculty members as Advisory Board/Editorial board of 27 research journals

98 Faculty members as Reviewer of 21 research journals

24 Faculty members as Conference Convener/Chair/Secretary in 16 Conferences

78 Faculty members as Reviewer in 25 Technical Conferences

61 Faculty members as Session Chairs/Moderators in 27 Conferences

115 Faculty members presented in international conferences

42 Faculty members as member of other 25+ Universities Statutory forums

45 Faculty members as member of National/International Committee/Boards/ Think Tanks

FACULTY MOBILITY

52 faculty members traveled abroad on international mobility of various time durations. These countries include Malaysia, USA, UK, China, Thailand, France, Germany, Switzerland, South Africa, Canada, New Zealand, Jordan, Italy, Qatar, Oman and Nepal.

PUBLIC AND SOCIAL SERVICE

Faculty members of NED University have been actively involved with various institutions and organizations assisting through their expertise. Some of the salient representations are as follows:

REPRESENTATION ON UNIVERSITIES STATUTORY AND TECHNICAL FORUMS

FACULTY AWARDS

NED University takes great pride in its dedicated and accomplished faculty, whose tireless commitment to teaching, research, and societal outreach continues to elevate the institution's standing. Their exceptional contributions are frequently recognized by national and international bodies, reflecting the high regard in which they are held by the broader community. The following are some notable awards and recognitions received by NED faculty members during the year 2024–25.

PEC Engineers' Excellence Award

Engr. Prof. Dr. Muhammad Tufail, Pro Vice-Chancellor of NED University, was conferred the PEC Engineers' Excellence Award – 2023 (Academia and Research) by the Pakistan Engineering Council. This prestigious recognition acknowledges his outstanding contributions to engineering education and research in Pakistan. The award highlights Dr. Tufail's pivotal role in advancing academic excellence and fostering innovation within the engineering community.

3rd Ali Suleman Habib Engineering Excellence Award

NED University team won the 3rd Ali Suleman Habib Engineering Excellence Award for the project Bringing Urdu into the Digital Age. The project, led by Dr. Saad Ahmed Qazi, Dr. Majida Kazmi along with team members Fauzia Yasir, Hamza Munir, and Syed Muhammad, was developed in collaboration with Anjuman-e-Taraqqi Urdu Pakistan and Ida Rieu Welfare Association. It focuses on preserving and digitizing the Urdu language and its literary assets. Dr. Usman Alauddin also received honourable mention for his remarkable contribution for his work in battery management system for electric vehicles. The award was presented by the House of Habib and The Institution of Engineers Pakistan (IEP).

ACECC Civil Engineering Achievement Award

Dr. Sarosh H. Lodi was selected as a recipient of the prestigious ACECC Civil Engineering Achievement Award 2025. Dr. Lodi was one of four individuals recognized at the 47th Executive Committee Meeting of the Asian Civil Engineering Coordinating Council (ACECC), held in Wellington, New Zealand. The award acknowledges his exceptional contributions to the field of civil engineering and will be formally presented at the 10th Civil Engineering Conference in the Asian Region (CECAR) in Jeju, South Korea.

UK Alumni Award 2025

Dr. Muhammad Abul Hasan, Associate Professor at NED University, was awarded the Science and Sustainability Award at the prestigious Study UK Alumni Awards. An alumnus of the University of Glasgow and co-lead of Pakistan's Neurocomputation Lab at the National Centre for Artificial Intelligence, Dr. Hasan was recognized for his impactful work in cognitive enhancement, which has positively influenced over 1,000 lives. His contributions in research and teaching have previously earned him Best Researcher and Best Teacher accolades.

IEP Engineering Excellence Awards

Dr. Sarosh H. Lodi, was awarded the Engineering Excellence Medal by the Institution of Engineers Pakistan (IEP) during the World Engineering Day (WED) celebrations held on March 4, 2025, in Islamabad. The event, aligned with UNESCO’s global observance of WED, recognized engineers contributing to the advancement of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN-SDGs). Dr. Lodi was honoured for his outstanding contributions to the field of engineering and academic leadership in Pakistan.

At the same event, Dr. Majida Kazmi, faculty member at NED University, was also awarded the Engineering Excellence Medal in recognition of her contributions in the fields of Artificial Intelligence and Computer Vision. Her work reflects the growing impact of emerging technologies on sustainable development and highlights the role of academic research in advancing engineering innovation in Pakistan.

Distinguished Innovation by Public Sector Award by the Global Innovation Institute

Project GreenED Solutions from NED University led by Dr. Saud Hashmi, Dr. Fahim Uddin and Engr. Shahzad Sheikh was honored as the only Pakistani winner of the 2024 Distinguished Innovation by Public Sector Award by the Global Innovation Institute (GII). The award recognized their innovative project "EcoPure"—an eco-friendly wetland system designed for industrial wastewater treatment. This achievement highlights NED University’s commitment to advancing sustainable environmental solutions through research and innovation.

NEDAASC Best Teacher Awards

- Dr. Shehnila Zardari (Professor) Department of Software Engineering
- Dr. Saeeda Nadir Ali (Associate Professor) Department of Chemistry
- Dr. Tariq Jamil (Assistant Professor) Department of Mechanical Engineering
- Engr. Syed Imran Ali (Lecturer) of Department of Petroleum Engineering

RESEARCH STATISTICS

31

Research
Centres

Rs 1.97 B

Research
Funding

233

Ongoing
Projects

143

Research
Staff

13

International
Conferences
held

RESEARCH CENTRES

The University houses **Thirty-one** state of the art research centres, which are actively involved in conducting hi-tech and hi-impact research. These centres are

Advanced Traffic Lab for Analytics and Simulation (ATLAS)	Smart City Lab, NCAI	National Centre for Cyber Security
Centre for Affordable Housing and Sustainable Built Environment	Neuro Computation Lab, NCAI	Electronic Design Centre
Centre for Advanced Studies in Renewable Energy (ASURE)	National Incubation Centre Karachi	K Electric Lab
Norwegian Centre for Petroleum Studies	National Centre for Robotics and Automation	Centre for Software Research and Development (CSRD)
Advanced Materials Testing Lab	Instrumentation Centre	DICE Energy Centre
Panjwani Hissar Water Institute	High Performance Computing Centre	National Centre for Big Data Analytics
Cowasjee Earthquake Centre	NED University Virtual Reality Centre	Building Information Modelling Centre
Product Development Centre	Heritage Cell	NED University Fire Lab
Centre for Quantum Technologies	Asma M. Hashmi STEM Centre	Centre for Nano Technologies
Centre for Gaming and Animation	Centre for Environment and Social Sustainability	Siemens Innovation Centre

Centre of Islamic Finance and FinTech

RESEARCH GRANTS

A total of 233 research projects worth Rs. 1,972 million have either won, on-going or completed in 2024-25. 126 projects are internally funded worth Rs. 188 million; whereas, 107 projects are externally funded worth 1,784 million, which is 92% of the total funding acquired. Similarly, Rs. 715 million (63.7%) funding is international whereas Rs. 1,257 million (36.3%) is from national sources including HEC GCF, HEC TTSF, HEC NRPU, HEC CPEC CRG, PSF and National Centres etc. It is worth mentioning that 26 projects worth Rs. 345 million are in the industrial consultancy category, which reflects the strong industrial linkage of NED University.

National vs International

Funding Amount (millions) and Proportion (%)

Research, Industrial Projects, National Centers

Funding Amount (millions) and Proportion (%)

RESEARCH PUBLICATIONS

As seen below, Scopus indexed research publications over the last few years published by NED University faculty have seen a rising trend.

During these years, the proportion of research publications categories are reflected in the figure below:

PATENTS

GRANTED PATENTS

- Smart Tactile Sensor Based Suture Force Attachment Measuring Instrument
 Inventor: Dr. Riaz Uddin (Electrical Engineering)
 Patent No.: 144343
 Granted: Jan 2025
- NED Ventilator Based on Controlled-Compressed Air/Oxygen Switching
 Inventor: Dr. Riaz Uddin (Electrical Engineering)
 Patent No.: 144344
 Granted: Jan 2025

FILED PATENTS

- Eco Track: Revolutionizing Carbon Footprint Awareness
 Inventor: Shehnila Zardari (Software Engineering)
- Med Scribe: Gen AI for Healthcare Documentation
 Inventor: Shehnila Zardari (Software Engineering)
- Fatty Acid Cellulose Esters & Packaging Films
 Inventor: Iftikhar Ahmed Channa (Metallurgical Engineering)
- Semiporous Cation-Conducting Blend Polymers for Electrolytic Processes
 Inventor: Shazia Perveen (Chemistry)
- Sugarcane Wax-Based Atorvastatin Nanoparticles
 Inventor: Saeeda Nadir Ali (Chemistry)
- Karachi Urban Observatory
 Inventor: Shehnila Zardari (Software Engineering)
- Sensor-Based Water Quality Monitoring (IoT)
 Inventor: Abdul Ghaffar (Environmental Engineering)
- Biodegradable pH-Responsive Packaging Films
 Inventor: Iftikhar Ahmed Channa (Metallurgical Engineering)
- Edible Packaging Films (Gelatin, Papaya, Soy Protein)
 Inventor: Iftikhar Ahmed Channa (Metallurgical Engineering)
- Motorcycle Helmet with Indicator & Antitheft Feature
 Inventor: Muhammad Zaid Khan (Industrial & Manufacturing Engineering)
- Tiles from Recycled Plastic
 Inventor: Ali Dad Chandio (Metallurgical Engineering)
- Satellite-Based Water Quality Monitoring with Google Earth Engine
 Inventor: Abdul Ghaffar (Environmental Engineering)
- Thermal Composite Block for Wall Insulation
 Inventor: Farnaz Batool (Civil Engineering)
- Customized Solar Distillation for Seawater Desalination
 Inventor: Abdul Ghaffar (Environmental Engineering)
- Dual-Channel Optical Network Communication System
 Inventor: Saba Ahmed (Telecommunication Engineering)

IN PROCESS

- **New Titanium Alloy for Biomedical Applications**
Inventor: Ali Dad Chandio (Metallurgical Engineering)
- **Crown Ethers from Fusidic Acid for Antioxidant and Anti-ulcer Use**
Inventor: Hira Sultan (Chemistry)
- **IntelliInspect: Real-Time Fabric Quality Inspection**
Inventor: Rizwan Aslam Butt (Telecommunication Engineering)
- **Cognitive & Sleep Enhancement via Binaural Beats**
Inventor: Muhammad Danish Mujib (Biomedical Engineering)
- **Soft Hybrid Nanogenerator for Green Energy**
Inventor: Muhammad Amir Qureshi (Textile Engineering)
- **Smart Industrial Liquid Level System**
Inventor: Riaz Uddin (Electrical Engineering)

NED University Journal of Research

Since 2013, the journal is published biannually in two sections, namely Structural Mechanics and Applied Sciences. The primary aim of this journal is to provide an international forum for the dissemination of research and new developments and their applications in engineering and technology. NED University of Journal of Research is a Scopus indexed Journal recognized by HEC. The Journal is also indexed by several other indexing services.

Journal of Research in Architecture and Planning (JRAP)

Focusing on research works relevant to the fields of architecture and planning, this journal explores issues of relevance to both scholars and practitioners. JRAP was initiated in 2000 and is a peer reviewed journal published biannually since 2011. The Journal is also recognized by HEC.

Journal of Social Sciences and Interdisciplinary Research (JSSIR)

Is a refereed, bi-annual journal. The journal acts as a forum for social scientists and researchers to investigate and discuss issues confronting societies both local and global. All the submitted manuscripts are multiple peer reviewed.

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES

Thirteen (13) international conferences were planned and held at NED University of Engineering and Technology this year in collaboration with several professional, industrial and government bodies including IEP Karachi Centre, HEC, SHEC and various other esteemed organizations:

- Leadership Conference on Industrial Linkage by Directorate of Industrial Liaison (DIL), August 3, 2024
- NED Women Conference 2024 - Women Empowerment for a Sustainable Future: Innovation, Enlightenment, and Pathways for Engendering Sustainable Development, November 6–7, 2024
- 4th International Conference on Innovations in Computer Science (ICONICS 2024), November 13–14, 2024
- 14th International Civil Engineering Conference (ICEC 2024) – Advancing Civil Engineering: Innovations for Achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals, November 15–16, 2024
- 4th International Conference on Advanced Materials and Process Engineering, December 18–19, 2024
- 2nd International Conference on Technology-Driven Climate Action (CLIMATECH-2025), January 16–17, 2025
- 2nd Conference on Architecture – History, Theory & Practice (CArch 2025), Theme: Architectural Encounters: Neo-liberalism and Localness – Conflicts and Solutions, January 31 – February 1, 2025
- 1st International Civil Engineering Symposium at TIEST, Mithi, January 31 – February 1, 2025
- 2nd International Conference on Computer Science and Applications (ICCSA 2025) at TIEST, Mithi, January 31 – February 1, 2025
- Global Conference on Green Construction, February 5–6, 2025
- 3rd International Annual Workshop on Big Data and Cloud Computing (BigC 2025), April 14–15, 2025
- 14th International Mechanical Engineering Conference (IMEC 2025) – Digital Transformation and Emerging Technologies in Mechanical & Manufacturing Engineering, April 25–26, 2025
- 4th International Biomedical Engineering and Digital Health Conference (IBDC 2025) – Fostering Entrepreneurship through sustainable innovation, May 2–3, 2025

UNIVERSITY IMPACT

NED University promotes sustainable development by aligning seven key components with the UN SDGs, making a significant impact. These components include undergraduate courses, final year projects, postgraduate courses, master's theses, university events, research publications, and externally funded research projects. The exercise mapped 3689 activities with 5311 instances across 17 SDGs.

Mapped **3689** activities with **5711** instances across 17 SDGs

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

SDG Legends

Overall SDG Mapping of impact components NED University

University Impact | Undergraduate Courses

During year 2024 and 2025, 861 courses at undergraduate level were offered. There were 1,457 mapping instances on SDGs. The following table shows the numerical mapping while the proportions are visualized below:

SDG	SDG	SDG	SDG	SDG	SDG	SDG	SDG									
SDG 1	SDG 2	SDG 3	SDG 4	SDG 5	SDG 6	SDG 7	SDG 8	SDG 9	SDG 10	SDG 11	SDG 12	SDG 13	SDG 14	SDG 15	SDG 16	SDG 17
27	52	188	27	39	88	142	460	96	42	105	47	41	16	38	22	27

University Impact | Final year design projects

565 Final year design projects (FYDP) were carried out at undergraduate level during year 2024 and 2025. There were 1,193 mapping instances on SDGs. The following table shows the numerical mapping while the proportions are visualized below:

SDG 1	SDG 2	SDG 3	SDG 4	SDG 5	SDG 6	SDG 7	SDG 8	SDG 9	SDG 10	SDG 11	SDG 12	SDG 13	SDG 14	SDG 15	SDG 16	SDG 17
16	16	98	51	11	40	82	120	288	29	155	122	81	16	25	12	31

University Impact | Postgraduate courses

During year 2024 and 2025, 524 postgraduate courses were taught at the master level. There were 1,613 mapping instances on SDGs. The following table shows the numerical mapping while the proportions are visualized below:

SDG 1	SDG 2	SDG 3	SDG 4	SDG 5	SDG 6	SDG 7	SDG 8	SDG 9	SDG 10	SDG 11	SDG 12	SDG 13	SDG 14	SDG 15	SDG 16	SDG 17
8	7	52	138	19	43	170	122	420	55	85	165	155	45	35	40	54

University Impact | Masters Theses

138 masters projects theses were undertaken during the year 2024–25. There were 423 mapping instances on SDGs. The following table shows the numerical mapping while the proportions are visualized below:

SDG 1	SDG 2	SDG 3	SDG 4	SDG 5	SDG 6	SDG 7	SDG 8	SDG 9	SDG 10	SDG 11	SDG 12	SDG 13	SDG 14	SDG 15	SDG 16	SDG 17
04	04	48	15	5	11	30	42	115	15	35	42	20	03	12	02	20

University Impact | University conferences, seminars and workshops

During year 2024 and 2025, about 125 activities including international conferences, seminars, workshops and other co- and extra-curricular activities were held across NED University campuses. These activities had 273 SDG mapping instances. The following table shows the numerical mapping while the proportions are visualized below:

SDG 1	SDG 2	SDG 3	SDG 4	SDG 5	SDG 6	SDG 7	SDG 8	SDG 9	SDG 10	SDG 11	SDG 12	SDG 13	SDG 14	SDG 15	SDG 16	SDG 17
03	03	08	42	24	06	10	42	33	25	15	18	11	03	03	10	17

University Impact | Research publications

Mapping of NED University research publications across 1-16 sustainable development goals (SDGs) as per data provided by Scopus over the last five years is presented here. There were 1695 publications mapping onto SDGs with over 8,000 citations. The following table shows the numerical mapping while the proportions are visualized below:

University Impact | Externally funded research projects

During year 2024-25, 107 externally funded projects were being actively pursued by faculty members. There were 459 mapping instances of these projects on SDGs. The following table shows the numerical mapping while the proportions are visualized below:

STRATEGIC PLAN 2024–2029

NED University of Engineering and Technology has set in motion an ambitious Strategic Plan for 2024–2029. This report provides a focused synthesis of critical parameters from the baseline data collected in 2024 and corresponding 2029 targets. It highlights high-impact improvements and strategically significant areas across the 12 pillars, demonstrating the University's commitment to transformation, academic excellence, and societal relevance.

Academic Excellence

NED University commits to launching new programmes annually, fostering innovation and relevance. Stakeholder engagement and international collaborations will enrich academic experiences, ensuring alignment with industry standards.

The University is realigning academic programs with future needs:

- Online and Hybrid Programs: Planned increase to 4, marking a 300% growth, indicating commitment to flexible, accessible learning.
- Postgraduate Thesis Leading to JCR Publications: A leap from 7% to 25% signals enhanced quality and rigor in research-based learning.

These milestones collectively reflect a shift toward quality, relevance, and intellectual visibility.

Faculty Development

Investment in faculty is pivotal for long-term excellence:

- Approved Patents: Increasing 1260% over 5 years, pointing to a vibrant innovation ecosystem.
- International Exposure: Faculty with overseas experience expected to grow from 5% to 16%, improving cross-border academic linkages.
- Research Publications in Indexed Journals: Doubling to 900 publications by 2029 reflects a culture of scholarship and impact-driven research.

These parameters align faculty performance with both national needs and international standards.

Student Success

Enabling well-rounded, employable graduates:

- National/International Awards: Growth from 27 to 98 awards reflects competitiveness and visibility of NED students.
- Entrepreneurial Alumni: Expansion in alumni driven startups or ventures by 200%, nurturing innovation-driven career pathways.
- Retention Rate (First-Year UG): Improved from 82% to 90%, showing better onboarding and student support mechanisms.

Such interventions support timely progression, graduate employability, and institutional reputation.

Infrastructure and Facilities

Modern facilities form the foundation for transformative education:

- New Facilities Developed: Tripling from to 99 by 2029, ensuring capacity for future academic growth.
- Upgraded Computer Centres: Expansion by 212%, supporting a digitally enabled campus.
- Green Spaces and Accessibility Enhancements: A consistent rise in inclusive and sustainable campus design supports the overall well-being of students and staff.

The focus is not just on expansion but on creating accessible, safe, and future-ready environments.

Professional Development

Equipping stakeholders with lifelong learning opportunities:

- Online/Blended Trainings Conducted: Tripling the number to 152, aligned with global trends in micro-credentialing and short courses.
- International Participation in Trainings: Increasing from 5% to 11% suggests expanding global relevance of NED's training offerings.

These efforts boost internal capacity and open pathways for revenue generation through external participants.

Industry Collaboration

Strengthening academic–industry linkages is a top priority:

- Cooperative Education Partners: Scaling from 25 to 128 – an increase of 412%, embedding practical exposure into academic programs.
- Faculty Engaged with Industry: Growth to 42 faculty (223%) enhances relevance and applied learning outcomes.
- Internships and Industrial Visits: Significant expansion in student exposure to industrial environments ensures work-readiness.

These initiatives enhance employability and create real-world relevance for curriculum and research

Internationalization

Broadening NED's global academic footprint:

- International Students Enrolled: Increase a 175% in international enrolment, highlighting global recognition and attractiveness of programs.
- Student Internships Abroad: Jumping from 1% to 4% (300% increase), enriching global exposure and intercultural skills.
- Strategic Global Partnerships: Expansion from 56 to 138 partnerships (146%), enabling academic exchange, collaborative research, and dual-degree initiatives.

This global outlook positions NED as a regional academic hub with a diversified student body and global engagement.

Alumni Engagement

Creating a networked community of support and advocacy:

- Engagement Activities: More than doubling from 23 to 55 (139%), reflecting deepening institutional ties with graduates.
- Alumni Satisfaction: Moderate but critical improvement from 72% to 80%, emphasizing meaningful and tailored engagement strategies.
- Mentorship & Career Support Initiatives: Increasing alumni participation in student mentorship programs adds value to both graduate employability and institutional goodwill.

Alumni serve as brand ambassadors and key partners in the university's future.

Service to Community

NED continues to engage directly with communities for inclusive development:

- Community Beneficiaries: Expanding from 5,410 to 9,732 (80%), reinforcing social impact and educational equity.
- Philanthropic University Events: Growth from 36 to 104 events reflects increasing emphasis on institutional responsibility.
- Volunteer Hours Contributed by Students: This metric also shows strong improvement, embedding values of service and empathy in students.

These efforts demonstrate NED's commitment to societal betterment and civic responsibility.

Research and Innovation

The push for high-quality, high-impact research is unmistakable:

- **Total Research Funding:** Doubling from PKR 2.1 billion to 5.0 billion underscores an aggressive funding strategy, essential for sustained research capacity.
- **Commercialized Products:** Fivefold increase to 25+ innovations brought to market signals growing relevance and entrepreneurship.
- **Interdisciplinary Research Centres:** Expansion 45 centres strengthens capacity for solving complex societal problems.

NED's research ecosystem is transitioning from volume-driven to value-driven outputs, aligned with national innovation priorities.

Digitalization

A future-ready university depends on robust digital transformation:

- **Digital Revenue Streams:** Reach to PKR 15 million before exponentially increasing this number, indicating new monetization models and digital outreach.
- **Participants in Digital Learning:** Targetting an exponential increase to 850 learners demonstrates scalable digital adoption.
- **Digitized Administrative Processes:** Rising 45 processes, showing efficiency and accountability in operations.

This leap reflects the university's focus on digital growth, resilience, and operational excellence.

Sustainability

Environmental and financial sustainability are long-term institutional goals:

- **Electricity from Renewable Sources:** Rising from 22% to 70%, significantly reducing carbon footprint.
- **SDG-Mapped Metrics:** Fourfold increase from 3,060 to 12,000 activities, reflecting alignment with global development agendas.
- **Financial Sustainability Index:** Improving from 65% to 85%, ensuring long-term fiscal health and independence.

Conclusion

NED University's Strategic Plan 2024–2029 is a bold, pragmatic, and data-driven blueprint for transformation. It commits to academic excellence, operational efficiency, research impact, global relevance, and social responsibility. With aggressive yet achievable targets—many projecting over 200% improvement—the University positions itself as a leader in higher education and a powerful engine of social and economic change.

CARBON FOOTPRINT PROFILE

Reporting Year: 2024-25

TOTAL CARBON EMISSIONS

SCOPE	DESCRIPTION	EMISSIONS (TONNES CO _{2E})
Scope 1	Direct emissions (campus vehicles, boilers, etc.)	1,512 MTeCO ₂
Scope 2	Indirect emissions (purchased electricity)	1,657 MTeCO ₂
Scope 3	Other indirect emissions (commuting, procurement)	19,200 MTeCO ₂

Note: These calculations have been made following GHG Protocol / ISO 14064

ENERGY CONSUMPTION

- Electricity consumption: ≈ 4,074,000 kWh
- Installed Solar Systems: 936kW
- Electricity generated through solarsystems: ~ 984,200 kWh (24%)

TRANSPORT AND MOBILITY

■ Vehicle

- Number of cars actively used and managed by the university: 44
- Average number of 4 and 2 wheelers vehicles (faculty and staff) entering the university daily: 1,260
- Number of shuttle buses operating: 15
- Number of Zero Emission Vehicles on campus per day: 2

■ Fuel Consumption

- Diesel generators: 5,170 litres.
- Campus vehicle fleet including HTV, LTV: 89,210 litres

WASTE MANAGEMENT

- Total waste generated: 360 tonnes
- Waste recycled or composted: 20%

WATER USAGE

- Total Water Consumption: 154,331 m³
- Water Recycling Systems: Yes
- Rainwater Harvesting: Yes

MITIGATION MEASURES UNDERTAKEN

- Installed rooftop solar: 936 kW
- Number of urban forests: 14
- Number of Awareness workshops on sustainability: 4 through CESS
- Healthy Friday to promote green mobility practices
- Maintenance of CO₂ Smart website by NED University

OFFICE OF RESEARCH INNOVATION AND COMMERCIALIZATION

The Office of Research, Innovation & Commercialization at NED University (ORIC-NEDUET) has consistently fostered a vibrant research culture by encouraging faculty and researchers to actively pursue national and international grants. In addition to managing ongoing projects, numerous research proposals have been submitted and are under review. ORIC's strategic efforts and institutional support have positioned it as one of the top-performing research offices in the country.

Achievements & Rankings:

- Scored 80 out of 100 in the HEC ORIC Annual Scorecard FY 2023–24.
- Ranked among the Top 03 'W' category ORICs out of 200+ universities/HEIs in Pakistan.
- Both ORIC and BIC at NED secured 'W' category rankings, a distinction held by only three universities nationwide.

Category-wise Rankings:

- 2nd in Human Resource and Operations
- 3rd in Research Excellence
- 5th in Innovation and Commercialization
- 5th in Sustainability and Capacity Building

Research & Grant Activity Summary

- 80 – SRSP (Sindh Research Support Programme – Sindh HEC) projects submitted
- 10 – SRSP projects awarded to faculty members
- 12 – SRSP projects successfully completed
- 02 – Erasmus+ Capacity Building in Higher Education proposals submitted
- 05 – NRP (National Research Programme for Universities) projects completed
- 07 – Research projects submitted to NADRA
- 30 – Training proposals submitted to NADRA
- 150 – NGIRI (National Grassroots ICT Research Initiative) proposals submitted
- 01 – HEC Technology Development Fund (TDF 4th Call) project approved
- 02 – Pakistan Academy of Sciences grants awarded

Innovation & Intellectual Property Summary

- 02 – Patent disclosures submitted
- 02 – Patents granted
- 21 – Patents filed
- 03 – Patent revisions in process
- 02 – Industrial designs submitted

Key Events & Capacity Building Highlights

- IP for Business Success Training – Two-day pilot seminar under IPO Pakistan’s IP Training Institute held on 4–5 September 2024.
- WIPO Treaty Stakeholder Consultation – ORIC participated in the national seminar on 2 October 2024, discussing IP protection and genetic resources.
- ASHRAE Leadership Visit & Conference – Visit by ASHRAE Society President and participation in the regional conference (3–7 October 2024).
- Training on Research Grant Proposal Writing – ORIC managers attended Sindh HEC training on 6 and 19 November 2024.
- Energy 4.0 Talk – Delivered by Dr. Muhammad Uzair as part of the ERASMUS CBHE initiative at NEDUET on 9 December 2024.
- Sindh HEC’s 4th Research Showcase – Co-hosted by NED University on 22–23 January 2025, promoting research visibility.
- Invent for the Planet 2025 – A global innovation event hosted at NED from 7–9 February 2025, with participation from six departments.
- HEC Journal Recognition Workshop – Organized at NEDUET on 10 April 2025, aimed at uplifting academic publishing standards.
- WIPO Inventor Assistance Program – ORIC representatives attended on 9 April 2025, strengthening IP awareness and capacity.
- Inauguration of the NED Intellectual Property Wall – Launched on 21 March 2025, celebrating 50+ significant institutional IPs

BUSINESS INCUBATION CENTRE

Mission:

- The Business Incubation Centre (BIC) at NED University of Engineering and Technology aims to assist engineering students, faculty, and researchers in transforming their innovative ideas into revenue-generating business models. BIC provides opportunities for commercial partners to invest in businesses with the potential to lead new industrial trends.

HEC Validated Business Incubation Center NEDUET in “W” Category for 2023–24

- Joint 1st Rank in Initiatives and Linkages
- Joint 1st Rank in Capacity Building and Mentoring

1st Dawlance Sustainability Hackathon, January 16th and 17th 2025

- Dawlance Sustainability Hackathon was conducted on January 16th and 17th 2025 co-organized by BIC (ORIC) and 2nd International Conference on Technology Driven Climate Action team, conducted by Departments of Telecommunications Engineering and Physics.
- A total of 90 teams from 8 universities registered to participate. Based on a formulated evaluation criteria, 24 teams from 6 universities were selected to compete under four sustainability themes set by the Dawlance Research and product development Team.
- Higher management of Dawlance including CEO, Mr. Umar Ahsan, CMO, Mr. Syed Hasan Jamil, Director Technologies, Mr. Harun Bingol, along with 16 mentors and experts from Dawlance attended and participated in the Hackathon, enabling effective industry academia interaction.

Entrepreneurship Bootcamps

- BIC (ORIC) organized “2-day Entrepreneurship Bootcamp” with Beaconhouse College A level on 30th and 31st July 2024. Day 01 activity included Design Thinking and Problem Definition, Turning ideas to prototypes and MVP and Elements of a BMC. Day 02 activity BMC Exercise (team activity), BMC presentations, Guest speaker sessions (Engr. Ansab Naqvi, CEO Asani.io, Engr. Sidra Shakeel, COO Fortify), Concluding remarks by Dr. Riaz Uddin (Director ORIC).
- Shell | Wafi Energy co-organized a one-day “The Big Idea” bootcamp on May 6th 2025. Around 40 students, researchers and faculty members participated in this certified bootcamp where Mr. Imran Azeem, Head of Training and Development and expert mentor and business coach provided guidelines and conducted Ideation activity.

Innovator Seed Fund (HEDP-ISF)

- Higher Education Commission Islamabad organized Investor Connect Event (ICE) on February 4th 2025. ISF 2023 awardee AirNex Global (Awardee: Mr. Irtiza Ali) was among the shortlisted startups to showcase their work at the event. The event was also attended by ISF 2023 focal person, Dr. Mirza Faizan from NEDUET.

Other notable activities

- Awareness session on “KE EPIC Challenge” conducted by Innoventures Global and K-Electric on 9th April 2025 for students and faculty.
- ORIC’s BIC hosted “Shell Tameer Awards 2024” session; NED secured 3 finalist spots, with one win in “Transportation and Mobility.”
- Over 100 NED students received USD 500 scholarships under Google Career Certificates Programme (IS & TD), concluded in Dec 2024.
- BIC and ORIC leaders served as judges for “Shark Tank Pakistan” auditions held from 12th–17th August 2024.
- Dr. Sundus Ali joined the “STEM Education” panel at IEP Karachi on 7th September 2024 to discuss academia-industry linkage.
- Dr. Sundus Ali participated in the 1st National Leadership Conference on Industrial Linkage on 3rd August 2024 at Marriott Hotel, Karachi.

ENGR. ABUL KALAM LIBRARY

The Engr. Abul Kalam Library at NED University stands as a leading engineering resource, boasting a vast collection that includes 87,967 books, access to 08 e-journal databases, over 34,543 e-books from Ebscohost Database, and the Elsevier Scopus Analytical Database. Its physical holdings encompass 692 journal titles and 30,589 items, catering to diverse research needs. Serving over 9,147 members, the library has facilitated over 112,610 research paper downloads and trained more than 1,048 students in library services, making it a crucial contributor to NED University's academic excellence.

87,967

Books in
Library

692

Hardcopy
Journal Titles

30,589

Hardcopy
Holdings

9,147

Library
Members

112,610

Research Paper
Downloads

1,048+

Students trained on
library services and
tools

10

E-Journals libraries
through HEC Digital
Library Access

QUALITY ASSURANCE

ISO 9000 certified since 2002 | Successfully transformed to ISO 9001:2015 standard

QEC cells have been established in all affiliated colleges and TIEST

QEC in “W” Category with 98% score in 2024-25

NED University established the Quality Management Cell (QMC) in 1999 to ensure quality assurance and continuous improvements in higher education. QMC successfully established a quality management system and acquired ISO 9000 certification in 2002. In 2012, NED University strengthened QMC and established the Quality Enhancement Cell (QEC) to equip the university with modern tools and techniques of quality assurance. NED-QEC has been instrumental in assuring quality in higher education within its campuses and affiliated colleges. In 2024-25, QEC NED continued to function with the spirit of continual improvement. The following are major highlights from 2024-25.

QEC Ranking

Since last five years, NED QEC stands in highest category of HEC, which is the “W” category. During the last assessment, NED QEC achieved score of 98%.

Memberships and Affiliations

NED QEC is partner member of three international and one national Quality Assurance Networks, whereas the QEC is the part of governing body of PNQAHEE. Following are the QA networks:

- Asia-Pacific Quality Network (APQN)
- The Talloires Network
- International Network for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (INQAAHE)
- Pakistan Network of Quality Assurance in Higher Education (PNQAHE)

Research Development Programme (RDP)

Annual Research Development Program (RDP) of 17 hours/ 07 sessions, training was conducted by 8 trainers for the faculty members and the refreshers from various departments. RDP was held between 9th to 24th April, 2025.

Following is the list of RDP trainings:

- | | |
|--|---|
| • Managing Research Projects | • Procurement Management |
| • Managing Human Resources on Projects | • Managing Research Accounts and Finances |
| • Effective Report Writing | • Writing Effective Research Proposa |
| • Travelling and Daily Allowance (TA/DA) | |

Faculty and Staff Training:

Other than RDP, EPS and Seminar a total of total 23 on campus training programmes were conducted and an overall of 806 faculty members, officers and staff of the university were trained. List of training is as under:

- Time Management & work life Management
- Basic Computer Skills and other IT tools
- Quality Management System
- Quality Management System
- First Aid & Fire Fighting
- Islamic Orientation
- Islamic Orientation
- Strategic Management Portal
- Health, Safety & Environment (Experiment based)
- Development of SAR as per HEC guidelines
- Departmental Website Update and its Management
- Effective Communications Skill
- Effective Quality Management Audits
- Using Generative Artificial intelligence (AI) tools in office work.
- Health, Safety & Environment
- Use of Generative Artificial intelligence (AI) for supporting functions
- Leadership & Team Development
- MS Power BI
- Negotiation & Conflict Resolution Skills
- Addressing Harassment at the workplace (laws and case studies)
- Balancing Work-life experience
- Effective Leadership/ Discovering Leadership through Self Analysis
- Assessment of SAR as per HEC guidelines

Internal and Surveillance Audits

Internal and Surveillance audits were arranged by the QEC during the year 2022-23 (till date) as per following details:

Internal Quality Audit	44th Internal Quality Audit: 19th and 20th December 2024	45rd Internal Quality Audit: 23rd to 25th April 2025
External Audit (LRQA)	SV2: 18th, 19th and 20th November 2024	
	SV3: 19th and 20th May 2025	

Internal and external auditors reported the “satisfactory” status of quality management system in NED University.

Effective PhD Supervision (EPS)

Effective PhD Supervision was jointly organized by QEC and ASRB from 7th to 14th October, 2024 for those faculty members who intended to attain NED PhD Supervisor status. Training was comprised of 10 hours and 07 sessions. Training sessions were conducted by 8 trainers.

Following is the list of RDP trainings:

- Introduction to PhD Supervision & University Regulations
- Effective Mentorship Techniques
- Research Methods and Guidance
- Managing Conflicts and Difficult Situations
- Ethical Considerations in Research
- Procurement
- Supporting Academic and Professional Development
- Intellectual Property and University Regulations

Feature activities of QEC

Some of the feature activities this year at NED QEC were:

■ Self-Postgraduate Program Review (PGPR)

The Self-Postgraduate Program Review (SPGPR) for all academic programs at the University was conducted on May 6–7, 2025. The review was carried out in accordance with the guidelines set by the Quality Assurance Agency (QAA) of the Higher Education Commission (HEC), Islamabad, for MPhil/MS and PhD programs. Mr. Syed Waqar ul Hassan, Director of QEC & Regulatory Affairs at Salim Habib University, served as the External Evaluator for the process.

■ Seminar on “HEC Policies for HEIs

Seminar on Quality Enhancement Cell of NED University of Engineering and Technology has organized a one-day awareness Seminar on “HEC Policies for HEIs” for Chairpersons and Faculty members of academic departments of the University. The seminar was held on January 29, 2025. Speakers of the seminar, Dr. Muhammad Wasif, Director QEC and Dr. Faaz Ahmed Butt, Dy. Director-I, QEC presented enlighten talks, exploring various aspects of the HEC policies.

NED ACADEMY

NED Academy is the professional development arm of NED University, offering industry-relevant training to students, graduates, and professionals. It focuses on building techno-managerial, leadership, and entrepreneurial skills. The Academy bridges academia and industry to drive career growth and national development.

Key Objectives

- Capacity Building of Participants – Offers skill-based certifications and diplomas.
- Promote Industry Linkages – Develops partnerships through corporate training programs.

Our Centres

- Centre for Continuing Engineering Education (CCEE) – Established in 1998; delivers technical, managerial, and legal trainings with over 10,000 participants trained.
- Centre for Multidisciplinary Postgraduate Programmes (CMPP) – Launched in 2008; provides hybrid/distance PG diplomas across engineering, IT, business, and education fields with 800+ graduates since 2020.

Collaborative Partners

Training Areas

No. of Participants

Revenue Chart

STATUTORY BODY MEETINGS

NED University pays due regards to holding of statutory meetings on time as per annual calendar. This allows the University functions and monitoring and evaluation processes to remain effectively placed. Each support function of the University is responsible for holding the meetings on time and to perform timely follow ups on action items as part of preparation for the next meeting.

Please find below some of the key statutory body meetings statistics for this year:

Statutory Bodies	Meeting frequency as per statutes	Held
Senate	01	01*
Syndicate	04	04+01* = 05
Academic Council	04	04+01* = 05
Board of Faculties (BOF) of various Faculties	04 for every faculty	15+07* = 22
Advanced Studies and Research Board (ASRB)	04	04
Finance Planning Committee (FPC)	04	04
University Development Working Party (UDWP)	04	04
Affiliation Committee	04	04

* Reporting for 2024-25

+ Emergent Meetings

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

The IT Department is responsible for providing, managing and planning all IT services at NED. We locally host complete data centre and private cloud, offering IT services to all campuses. These services include Enterprise Resource Planning software, Learning Management Systems, secured email service and various research journals fully automated management software.

Endeavouring to provide cutting-edge technology solutions for enhancing the teaching methodology and support research. The ITD offers the following services:

- 24 x 7 Network Operations
- Various web-based services (Web, DNS, and email etc.)
- Infrastructure development and enhancement
- Indigenous Software development services
- Complete support and guidance

As the world has transformed during the past year, ITD has addressed the presented challenges with confidence and high commitment. There are several highlights of the year – some are presented below:

HEC DLSEI Programme:

Throughout the past year NED was the leading university collaborating with HEC in its offering of MOOC programme i.e., digital learning and skill enhancement Initiative. Sr. Manager Network & Hardware was NED focal person for the programme. The highest number of learner registrations as well as the most number of course registrations were done by NED.

PERN:

The PERN connectivity and bandwidth has been further enhanced this year with whopping speeds at all three campuses as well TIEST as under:

Links	Speed
Main Campus	653 Mbps (PERN: 160 Mbps, Smart University: 493 Mbps)
LEJ Campus	51 Mbps (PERN:20Mbps, Smart University: 31 Mbps)
City Campus	20 Mbps
TIEST	50 Mbps
Total Bandwidth	774 Mbps

Infrastructure Development

■ Expansion of WiFi:

During the past year blanket WiFi coverage was extended incorporating CIS, Food Engineering, Boys Hostel.

■ Extension of LAN:

Fibre optic and UTP LAN connectivity was extended to Academic Block2, Norwegian Centre, Food Engineering, Economics and Management Sciences.

■ Computer labs in various departments:

New computer labs were setup in Food Engineering, Economics and Management sciences, CCEE.

■ Smart Classroom in Computational Finance:

A new smart classroom was built in the Department of Mathematics and Computational Finance.

License renewals

In order to keep the operations running and maintaining quality of services is valued the most by ITD. Various licences / subscriptions were renewed this year to keep all services and equipment updated.

HEC Data Centre

Work on HEC Data centre for South region had been initiated. This data centre is being established by HEC in NEDUET.

Support beyond University

Playing its part in ITC support and extending its services to other organizations. ITD Data Centre had provide hosting services to Sindh HEC (Job Portal) and PEC Journal of Research.

MEDICAL DEPARTMENT

NED University's Medical Department is committed to ensure the wellbeing of the University's workforce and students. Here are some highlights of the medical services provided during 2024-25:

- 708 Students were treated in both emergency and out-patient in main campus as well as both peripheral medical sub-centres located at LEJ and City campuses.
- 2,260 Employees and their dependents received treatment in emergency and out-patient at both of main campus as well as peripheral sub-centres at LEJ and City campuses.
- 1,349 Employees and their dependents received inpatient treatment at both direct panel/enlisted reimbursement hospitals.
- 2,357 Candidates for undergraduate programme were examined for issuance of Medical fitness in 2024-25.
- 09 Employees were examined for provisional medical fitness at the time of recruitment in 2024-25.
- The medical department offers various diagnostic Pathological/Radiological tests and provides counselling for cognitive assessment, psychological wellbeing, and stress management on a case-by-case basis.
- The Medical Department also organizes health awareness programmes time to time.

UNIVERSITY ADVANCEMENT & FINANCIAL ASSISTANCE

Established in 2014 at NED University to support academic advancement, community engagement, and integration of SDGs in higher education.

Activities of UAFA

UAFA continues to promote research, innovation, community service, and sustainability through student and faculty engagement. Efforts align with the university's vision to contribute towards national development and UN SDGs, with a focus on women's empowerment and inclusive education.

Showcasing of Best Final Year Projects (FYPs) – 2024

Top projects across departments were exhibited under two themes:

- Linked to UNESCO Chair “Sustainable Urban Regions” – SDG 11 & allied goals.
- Related to other SDGs – tackling societal, environmental, and economic challenges through technology and innovation.

Projects reflected interdisciplinary solutions in engineering, social sciences, and finance. Alumni and businesses were encouraged to adopt and invest in these ideas.

SCAN TO VIEW
BEST FYPs - 2024

Showcasing of Best Final Masters' Theses

Top postgraduate theses related to sustainable urban development under the UNESCO Chair were displayed to promote advanced research.

SCAN TO VIEW
BEST MASTER THESES
SPRING 2025

SCAN TO VIEW
BEST MASTER THESES
FALL 2024

Events

■ Interactive Workshop on Journalism

Held on 5th October 2024, featuring renowned journalists (Dawn, The News, Jang). Students from all programs attended the enriching session.

■ Seminar on Disability Rights & Accessibility

On 27th Nov 2024, experts from HANDS Pakistan, Sindh HEC, and IDA REIU emphasized inclusion strategies. HANDS donated 5 wheelchairs to NED.

■ Symposium – Solidarity with Kashmir

Held on 4th Feb 2025 under the theme 'Understanding the Kashmir Challenge', with distinguished speakers from foreign and military services.

■ Representation of NED University at Career Fair

UAFA represented NED at Ziauddin University's Career Fair (Feb 2025), promoting postgraduate admissions.

■ The NED Experience

This alumni magazine celebrates the contributions and memories of NEDians worldwide. The latest version was published in 2023.

SCAN TO VIEW
READ PAST EDITIONS

SCAN TO VIEW
SUBMIT ARTICLES

■ NED Alumni Network & Alumni Engagement

Held on 4th Feb 2025 under the theme 'Understanding the Kashmir Challenge', with distinguished speakers from foreign and military services.

UAFA facilitates alumni with documents, messages for events, and university updates. Personalized greetings are shared regularly.

Membership Stats: Lifetime Members: 302, Associate Members: 35,744, Friends: 33

NATIONAL INCUBATION CENTRE, KARACHI

Nestled within NED University Campus, the National Incubation Center Karachi (NIC Karachi) stands as a testament to fostering economic growth in Sindh and Pakistan. Established in May 2018, NIC Karachi is an ignition point for aspiring entrepreneurs, funded by the national technology fund Ignite and operated by LMKT.

NIC Karachi fosters a dynamic environment for innovation by forging partnerships with industry leaders on both the international and local fronts. Renowned institutions like INSEAD and Orbit Startups bring a global perspective, while local heavyweights such as YBG provide invaluable regional expertise and support. Through this collaborative network, NIC Karachi has empowered over 376 startups through its incubation and acceleration programs.

376

Start-ups incubated

180

Graduated start-ups

10 B

Revenue Generated (PKR)

12 B

Investment Raised (PKR)

July 2024

- MoU between NEDUET and Rashid Latif Cricket Academy
- MoU between NEDUET and Indus Hospital & Health Network
- MoU between NEDUET and Helping Hand for Relief and Development

August 2024

- MOU between NEDUET and Tech Vally Pvt Ltd and Information, Science & Technology Department Government of Sindh
- Cultural, Educational and Scientific Cooperation between Faculdades Catolicas, sponsor of Pontificia Universidade Catolica do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil and NED University of Engineering & Technology, Pakistan
- MOU between Educational, Research and Technological Cooperation between Bu-Ali Sina University and NED University of Engineering & Technology, Karachi
- MOU: Information Science and Technology, Government of Sindh and NED University (offering IT Educational Training Programs)
- MOU between NEDUET and Beaconhouse National University (BNU) Lahore Pakistan

September 2024

- Contract Agreement between DreamBig (Pvt.) Ltd. and NED University of Engineering & Technology, Karachi
- MOU between Nanjing University of Information Science and Technology Nanjing (China) and NED University of Engineering & Technology, Karachi
- Agreement on Co-Construction of China-Pakistan "Belt and Road" Joint Laboratory on Smart Disaster Prevention of Major Infrastructures and Academic Exchange between Southeast University, Nanjing (China) and NED University of Engineering & Technology, Karachi
- MoU between Confucius Institute University of Karachi & NED University of Engineering & Technology (Jointly Launch Chinese Language Compulsory Program).

October 2024

- MOU Pakistan Cables Ltd. and NED University To Provide Academic Scholarship Opportunities to underprivileged female students enrolled in the Electrical Engineering Department.

November 2024

- MOU Youth Ambassador Programme: Art Council of Pakistan Karachi and NED University
- MOI Algorithm energy and NED University of Engineering & Technology
- MOI IPCS (Ideal Proposition Cyber Security) Riyadh Saudi Arabia / MCS (Meraal Cyber Security) Lahore and NED University.

December 2024

- Agreement: M/s Siemens Pakistan Engineering Co. Ltd. and NED University
- MOI Risk Associates Pvt Ltd and NED University (Prof. Dr. Mubashir Khan, Chairperson CS&IT)
- MOU LuckyOne Mall and NED University of Engineering & technology regarding establish a framework for collaboration on cyber security internet of things (IoT) and computer vision CV Based research and development (R&D) Projects etc. Artificial intelligence (Stem Education).

January 2025

- MOU between National Database and Registration Authority (NADRA) and NED University of Engineering & Technology

February 2025

- Work of Art Loan Agreement NED and Ava Ardeshir Cowasjee On Permanent Loan from the Personal Collection
- MoU NED and EHHED Sonsulting Limited to develop the funding structure & raising funds for commercialization of its STE projects
- MoU between NEDUET with NED Alumni Association Canada and RentAKloud
- MoU between NED UET and Sindh Economic Zone Management Company (SEZMC)
- Agreement of Cultural, Educational and Scientific Cooperation between Baskent University, Ankara, Turkey and NED UET, Karachi
- MOI NED and Toronto Metropolitan University (TMU) Canada

March 2025

- MoU between NEDUET with Global Innovatrix (Pvt.) Ltd.
- MoU between NED UET and Hamdard University
- MoI NED Scholars and NED University
- Project Completion Agreement between NED University of Engineering & Technology and Anjuman Taraqqi Urdu Pakistan
- MOU regarding Grow with Google Career Certificates Scholarship 2025 MOU Tech Valley and Sindh Government and NED

April 2025

- MoU between ASHRAE Pakistan Chapter and Centre for Environment and Social Sustainability (CESS) and NEDUET
- MOU Resolve-Research Solution & Ventures (south) (research facility at the National Centre of Remote Sensing and Geoinformatics (NCRG) with the SUPARCO complex) and NED University.

May 2025

- MOU Pakistan Freelancers Association (PAFLA) and Thar Institute of Engineering, Sciences and Technology, TIEST
- Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) with Dineticq Limited and NED University of Engineering & Technology, Karachi
- MOU articulates a mutual understanding between Akhter Hameed Khan Foundation (AHKF) and NED University of Engineering & Technology, Karachi.

Meezan Bank
The Premier Islamic Bank

MoU SIGNING CEREMONY

MEEZAN BANK AND NED UNIVERSITY OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY

ESTABLISHMENT OF CENTRE OF FINANCE AND BANKING (CIFF)

PROMINENT VISITORS

Academic Visitors / University Delegations

- 29 August 2024: Mr. Talha Uzun from Istinye University Istanbul
- 03 October 2024: Dr. Ahmed Tamkin Butt from University of Nottingham
- October 2024: Dr. Zhang Xiaoping from Sichuan Normal University, China
- 29 January 2025: Dr. Tillal Eldabi (University of Bradford) and Dr. Mariati Yousf (National University of Malaysia)
- 20 February 2025: High-level delegation from Toronto Metropolitan University led by President Dr. Mohamed Lachemi
- 08 April 2025: Prof. Dr. Shahed Anwar Khan from Curtin University, Perth, Australia

Government Officials / Diplomats

- 24 July 2024: Rana Mashhood, SA to PM and Chairman of PMYP
- 26 July 2024: Nadeem Irshad Kayani, Federal Secretary IPC GoP
- 26 September 2024: H.E. Nakagawa Yasushi, Deputy Consul General of Japan
- 14 April 2025: Federal Minister Prof. Ahsan Iqbal at Workshop on Big Data and Cloud Computing
- 19 February 2025: Federal Minister Prof. Ahsan Iqbal inaugurated HEC Data Centre
- December 2024: H.E. Andrey Fedorov, General Consular of Russian Federation in Karachi
- 19 December 2024: H.E. Mr. Cemal Sangu, Consul General of Türkiye
- 14 April 2025: H.E. Mr. Cemal Sangu gave a talk on academic pathways and scholarships
- 24 April 2025: H.E. Nakagawa Yasushi delivered a speech in fluent Urdu

Industry Leaders / Corporate Representatives

- 08 July 2024: Former Pakistan cricket captain Rashid Latif
- 30 July 2024: Dr. Bari visited for MoU signing with Indus Hospital
- 14 October 2024: Pakistan Cables leadership (Arshad Shafiq, Aadil Riaz, Maryam Durrani)
- 11 November 2024: Mr. Saquib Saeed, CEO of Algorithm Energy
- 26 November 2024: Kamal Mahmood Mian, MD FAST Cables
- 12 December 2024: Siemens leadership including Syed Muhammad Daniyal, MD
- 30 December 2024: Saad Zubari, CEO Lucky One Mall
- 11 February 2025: Honda senior management via DECE and Dr. Hashim
- 21 November 2024: Mr. Salman Mushtaq Qureshi, Founder of Meraal Cyber Security

Industry Leaders / Corporate Representatives

- 02 September 2024: Mr. Lloyd Wright from Asian Development Bank
- 21 November 2024: World Bank team including Imran ul Haq, Sana Ahmed & Sarah Khokhar
- 10 March 2025: World Bank delegates Anna C. O'Donnell and Christian Albert Peter
- 26 February 2025: Mr. Shujauddin Shaikh visited, met leadership, and addressed students
- 09 January 2025: ASHRAE delegation (Engr. Mehmood Ahmed, Engr. Shuja Khalid, Engr. Abbas Sajid, Dr. Uzair, Engr. Akbar Zaheer)

ALUMNI ENGAGEMENT & SUPPORT

NED University is proud to have an active and vibrant relationship with its alumni across the world. Here is a map showing the global spread of NED alumni who are on contact with NED University via its social media platform. There are many more who enjoy physical connection with their alma mater. NED alumni are a huge source of support, advice and hand holding for their alma mater.

During the year 2024–25, NED University witnessed remarkable generosity from its distinguished alumni and alumni associations across the globe. Contributions and donations amounted to over Rs. 250 million, significantly enhancing the University's infrastructure, academic environment, and student support systems. A glimpse of these impactful contributions is as follows:

- Engro Powergen Thar Limited (EPTL), through the efforts of Engr. Ahsan Zafar, funded the establishment of a Baby Daycare Centre, which was completed and inaugurated at the NED University.
- Numerous prominent alumni and international NED alumni associations contributed extensively towards scholarship and financial assistance programmes. Notably, Engr. Aftab Rizvi played a pivotal role in founding the MaaJee Scholarship Endowment Fund, which now enables over 300 students annually to pursue higher education in engineering.
- The NEDAASC chapter continued its annual tradition of recognizing academic excellence by awarding certificates and cash prizes to faculty and students under the categories of Best Researcher, Best Teacher, and High-Impact Final Year Projects.
- Ashraf Habibullah generously funded multiple initiatives, including:
The installation of a 100 KW solar system, renovation and façade uplifting, rainwater flooding mitigation, and establishment of a smart classroom at the City Campus, all of which were completed and inaugurated in February 2025.
- Through NEDIAN-NA, he also supported the renovation of the Civil Engineering Lecture Hall, installation of two shading kiosks, donation of 25 desktop computers, and furnishing and interior development of the historic Chimney Building at the City Campus.
- The Makhdoomi CAD Lab was established in the Department of Civil Engineering through the generous donation of Engr. Amir ul Islam
- The construction of courtyards and an ablution area adjacent to the Civil Engineering block was funded by Paragon Constructors Pvt. Ltd., led by Engr. Aftab Siddiqui.
- The UKAA Baltimore Chapter extended its support towards STEM development programmes at NED University.
- HabibMetro contributed to the construction of the Wall of Fame at the Main Campus, commemorating notable achievements and milestones

SPECIAL MENTIONS

Launch of Pak-Türkiye Media Centre at NED Academy

On December 19, 2024, NED University of Engineering & Technology hosted the inauguration ceremony of the Pak-Türkiye Media Centre at NED Academy in the Senate Hall. The event involving the ribbon cutting ceremony featured speeches by Mr. Dursun Ali YAŞACAN, TİKA, and Mr. Cemal Sangu, Türkiye's Consul General.

Live Streaming

From PAK TÜRKIYE MEDIA CENTRE
NED University, Karachi, Pakistan

Extension of Faculty Executive Centre and Girls Hostel at NED University

With support from the Federal and Sindh Governments, NED University has expanded its on-campus accommodation. The Foreign Faculty Guest House now includes 12 furnished suites and a dining area for visiting faculty and international guests. The Girls Hostel has also been extended with 25 new rooms, providing safe housing for over 50 female students and meeting the needs of a growing student population.

Launch of Astrolabes Data Centre at NED University

The HEC launched the "Astrolabes Data Centre" at NED University, on February 20, 2025. This state-of-the-art data centre, designed for high-performance computing, aims to revolutionize Pakistan's educational infrastructure. It was inaugurated by Federal Minister for Planning, Development and Reforms, Mr. Ahsan Iqbal.

Inauguration of the Centre of Environment and Social Sustainability (CESS)

On March 10, 2025, the Centre of Environment and Social Sustainability (CESS) was inaugurated at NED University with support from the World Bank. The event included a guided tour of the new facility, and a launch ceremony at the NED Auditorium. Attended by senior representatives from the World Bank, academia, and the development sector, the event marked the Centre's role in advancing research, training, and consultancy in environmental and social safeguards. CESS has already conducted three training programmes for PIU officials, consultants, and academics, and signed an MoU with ASHRAE Pakistan to support collaborative efforts in sustainability.

Panjwani Hisar Water Institute (PHWI)

The Panjwani-Hisaar Water Institute (PHWI), a joint initiative of NED University, the Panjwani Charitable Foundation, and the Hisaar Foundation, is contributing significantly to education and research in sustainable water management. Through its Master of Engineering Management program and a specialized course on Water Law, PHWI is building interdisciplinary capacity to address urban water and climate challenges, shaping both academic and practical approaches to water governance.

NED EnerTech Science and Technology Park

The NED-EnerTech Science and Technology Park, established through an agreement with Kuwaiti state-owned EnerTech, has made key progress this year. The Sindh Cabinet approved a 3-acre land increase and revised project funding of PKR 1.7 billion to be routed through NED University. The upcoming milestone is the concession agreement signing, enabling full-scale development of this integrated science and technology hub.

Inauguration of High-Performance Sports Research Centre at NED University

During his visit to NED University, Federal Minister Prof. Ahsan Iqbal inaugurated the High Performance Sports Research Centre. The Centre is part of HEC’s establishment of Sports Academic and Youth Olympics – PM Youth Programme. The Centre is equipped to support advanced sports diagnostics, rehabilitation, and research, aiming to enhance athletic performance through modern technology and evidence-based practices.

NED Alumnus Raghiv Hussain joins Altera as CEO

In a proud moment for NED University and Pakistan, Intel announced in May 2025 the appointment of Raghiv Hussain as CEO of Altera, making him the first Pakistani to lead a unicorn company. His first address as CEO Altera shows NED logo in the background with CEOs of Intel and Silverlake also in the picture. A distinguished NED alumnus, Raghiv previously co-founded Cavium, which was acquired by Marvell for USD 6 billion in 2018. Raghiv Hussain visited NED University in February 2025 to attend the NED Alumni Convention, where he addressed the audience and engaged with students in an inspiring fireside chat.

Thar Institute of Engineering, Science and Technology

The Thar Institute of Engineering, Science and Technology (TIEST) in Mithi, Tharparkar— a constituent college of NED University—offers BS Computer Science and BE Civil Engineering programmes, both well accredited by relevant regulatory bodies. The BS Computer Science programme celebrated the graduation of its first batch in 2023, while the first batch of Civil Engineering students is expected to graduate in 2025. Transition to its new campus is planned for the next fiscal year.

Launch of Siemens Innovation Centre

The Siemens Innovation Centre was launched at NED University to provide hands-on training in automation, SCADA, and control systems. This partnership offers students real-world experience on industrial-grade platforms, marking a leap in practical engineering education.

NEDIAN Alumni Convention 2025

The NEDIAN Alumni Convention 2025 was held on February 22, 2025, at the NED University Main Campus, celebrating the outstanding achievements of NED graduates from around the world. Organized by the NED International Alumni Network (NEDIAN) Association – Pakistan, the event brought together hundreds of alumni, including renowned figures such as Engr. Safwan Shah, Engr. Raghیب Hussain, Engr. Ashraf Habibullah, and Engr. Amir ul Islam. The convention served as a vibrant platform to recognize the remarkable contributions of NEDians across various fields, fostering a deep sense of pride, connection, and unity within the global alumni community.

Documentation of Traditional Houseboats at Manchar Lake

A major community outreach and conservation project was recently completed by the Heritage Cell, Department of Architecture and Planning, under the leadership of Prof. Dr. Anila Naeem and Architect Farida Abdul Ghaffar. Supported by the CPF, UK and the British Council, the project focused on safeguarding the last surviving houseboats—locally known as Galiyo—of the Mohanna fishing community at Manchar Lake, Sindh. These traditional flat-bottomed boats, typically 35–38 feet long and 10 feet wide, serve as floating homes for lake-dwelling families. The project restored 44 houseboats and improved living conditions.

UNIVERSITY FINANCES AND KPIs

FINAL DEMAND BUDGET ESTIMATES (2024-25) (IN PKR MILLIONS)

No.	Particulars	Recurring	Recurring TIEST	Self Finance	UDWP	Research	CCEE
1.	Total Receipts	5,523.714	442.921	485.200	84.456	156.758	407.500
2.	Total Payments	5,521.974	374.714	485.200	84.456	154.300	407.000
3.	Closing Balance	1.740	68.207	-	-	2.458	0.500

DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS (IN PKR MILLION)

Name of Project	PC-1 Provision	Releases up to 31.03.2025	Amount Utilized /committed up to 31.03.2025	Expected Date of Completion
Establishment of 21st Century Water Institute (PSDP 2021-22)	470.000	470.000	466.732	Completed (December 2024)
Establishment of Sports Academies (High Performance & Resource Centers) and Youth Olympics – HEC (PSDP 2021-22 Umbrella Project of HEC)	293.323	223.020	223.020	December 2025 (subject to release of funds)
Enhancement of Academic facilities at NED University (PSDP 2021-22)	1537.345	500.000	434.000	June 2027
Strengthening of Lab facilities in 05 leading Engineering Universities (including NED University)	1,576.709 NED Share	Awaited	Awaited	June 2028
Construction of Girls Hostel at NED University (ADP Project)	149.841	149.841	61.314	June 2025
Establishment of Thar Institute of Engineering, Sciences and Technology, at Mithi, Tharparkar (ADP Project)	3141.583	311.100	289.364	June 2026

NED UNIVERSITY FUNDS

as on 30-04-2025

No.	Name of Fund	Total in Million (PKR)
1.	NED University Endowment Fund	4,600.985
2.	MOST Endowment Fund	420.604
3.	Oman IT Chair Fund	360.798
4.	Rafeeqi Endowment Fund	9.376
5.	Pension Fund	2,967.250
6.	G. P. Fund	1,173.064
7.	Benevolent Fund	224.942
8.	Research Fund	90.000
9.	UDWP	160.000
10.	Maa Jee Endowment Fund	87.950
11.	Sultana & Burj Endowment Fund	1.500
12.	Student Support Fund	42.295
13.	TIEST Endowment Fund	377.638
14.	Others	661.012
Total		11,177.414

COST PER STUDENT

PROPORTION OF REVENUE STREAMS TOWARDS MEETING COST OF STUDENT (2024-25)

KEY INDICATORS

No.	Key Ratios	2023-24	2024-25	2025-26 (Planned)
1.	Faculty to Staff Ratio	1 : 2.6	1 : 2.6	1 : 2.4
2.	Faculty to Student Ratio	1 : 17	1:18	1:18
3.	Self-Generated Income as %age of total Resources	51%	40%	42%
4.	Recurring Grant (Federal HEC) as %age of total Expenditures	24%	20%	18%
5.	Recurring Grant (GoS) as %age of total Expenditures	25%	40%	40%
6.	Students Fees as %age of Cost per student	30%	32%	32%
7.	Salary as %age of Total Expenditure	70%	69%	68%
8.	Non-Salary as %age of Total Expenditure	30%	31%	32%

MAIN CAMPUS

University Road, Karachi, 75270
Ph: +92 (0)21 99261261-8
Fax: +92 (0)21 99261255

LEJ CAMPUS

81-A, Block-3, Memon
Co-operative Housing
Society, Karachi.
Ph: +92 (0)21 99230602-4
Fax: +92 (0)21 99230602

CITY CAMPUS

Maulana Din Muhammad
Wafai Road, Karachi. 74200
Ph: +92 (0)21 99213058
Fax: +92 (0)21 32620793

Thar Institute of Engineering Science and Technology (TIEST)

(A constituent college of NED University
of Engineering & Technology)
Shaheed Benazir Bhutto Cultural
Complex, Police Road, Near SSP Office,
Mithi Tharparkar.

**SCAN THE
QR CODE
TO VIEW THIS
REPORT ONLINE**

